

CONCEPT OF THE “BEAUTY” AND ITS SYNONYMS

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Annotatsiya: *Maqolaning maqsadi go'zallik tushunchasining tavsifi va ifodasini aniqlash, shuningdek turli manbalarga ko'ra ta'riflar va sinonimlarni o'z ichiga oladi.*

Аннотация: *Цель статьи - выявить описание и выражение понятия красота, а также включить в него определения и синонимы по разным источникам.*

Annotation: *The purpose of the article is identifying the description and expression of the concept beauty as well as it includes definitions and synonyms according to the different sources.*

Key words: *beauty, dictionary, definition, synonym.*

Throughout history, beauty has been extolled, revered, dismissed, and argued about. It has been regarded as some fundamental property with perfectionistic connotations, or it has been equated with truth. According to an adage, it is only "skin deep" and "in the eye of the beholder." The discussion today is an attempt to develop a coherent and defensible concept of beauty. I'll start with definitions and then discuss beauty from a variety of perspectives.

Beauty is commonly described as a feature of objects that makes these objects pleasurable to perceive. Such objects include landscapes, sunsets, humans and works of art. Beauty, together with art and taste, is the main subject of aesthetics, one of the major branches of philosophy. As a positive aesthetic value, it is contrasted with ugliness as its negative counterpart. Along with truth and goodness it is one of the transcendentals, which are often considered the three fundamental concepts of human understanding.

The word beautiful in English is a borrowing from French, going back to the Latin bellus, which, in turn, goes back to the word bonum - good. Thus, the idea of beauty is a concretization of a general positive sign. In this sense, it can be noted that the semantic convergence of a general positive assessment and an aesthetic positive assessment is probably a natural

evaluative qualification of objects, and this qualification is carried out in a shuttle mode: good - beautiful - good, hence the “beautiful deed”. The word pretty is interpreted in the English etymological dictionary as crafty, wily, clever, ingenious, fine, brave, beautiful in a slight or dainty manner, considerable in quantity and goes back to the Germanic *pratt- trick. The dictionary contains a very important reasoning: the development of the meaning of this word is parallel to the development of the semantics of other words - canny, clever, cunning, fine, nice (ODEEtym). We see that the words denoting particular positive qualities "smart", "able", etc., moved into the category of general evaluative ones, and those words were again concretized to designate beauty.

Dictionaries refer to beauty as giving aesthetic pleasure or pleasure of the senses. But, since aesthetic pleasure is defined as pleasure derived from the appreciation of beauty, this doesn't help. “Pleasure of the senses” might imply something like the pleasure of being stroked or massaged, but this seems inadequate as an example of beauty. Dictionaries also refer to beauty as being perfection of form. But what are the criteria for perfect on? Something like a balanced combination of dissimilar elements, perhaps? But many things we regard as beautiful are neither perfect nor complex. The French novelist Stendhal described beauty as “the promise of happiness”, commenting that “there are as many styles of beauty as there are types of happiness”. But beauty seems to be a presence not just a promise, and happiness is not entirely the same as pleasure.

Here are two tentative definitions:

- Beauty is the quality by which something gives pleasure to someone for reasons other than mental stimulation, personal gain or the satisfaction of innate drives. The pleasure may be aroused by a thing or an artistic representation or an action or an idea.
- Beauty is the quality by which something gives pleasure to someone directly through the intellect and independent of any ulterior considerations.

These definitions include no description of the type of pleasure imparted by beauty, nor of the particular sense by which the beauty is experienced. They assume that the presence of beauty is decided by admirers. This is consistent with the view that “beauty is in the eye of the beholder” but it goes beyond that. It might imply that nothing is either beautiful or not beautiful unless it is being exposed to someone and/or being thought about by someone.

The conceptual characteristics of the concept "beauty" are revealed in the dictionary interpretations of synonyms denoting this concept. Turning to the English Synonymous Dictionary (WNDS), we find the following distinctions:

1. A common feature for the synonyms beautiful, lovely, handsome, pretty, bonny, comely, fair, beauteous, pulchritudinous, good-looking is the quality of "pleasure when contemplating". The dictionary specifically stipulates that the pleasure in contemplating beauty is sensual or aesthetic. It is important to note that the opposition of 1) directly sensual and 2) aesthetic as mentally mediated contemplation underlies the identification of aesthetics as a special field of knowledge.

2. Differential features of compared synonyms are grouped in the following directions:

- a) mentally mediated contemplation (mind and soul) (beautiful);
- b) perfection, conformity to the ideal (beautiful);
- c) intense emotional admiration, fascination (lovely);
- d) rational (non-emotional), distant pleasure action from the contemplation of perfection (handsome);
- e) subtlety, grace, delicacy of the contemplated object (usually but small in size) (pretty);
- f) emphasis on the pleasure of (sensual) contemplation of an object (bonnie);
- g) harmony, proportionality and opposition to simple mu, ordinary (comely);
- h) emphasizing the purity, impeccability and freshness of the subject contemplation (fair);
- i) emphasis on bodily beauty (sometimes with ironic overtones) (beauteous, pulchritudinous);
- j) a lower degree of expressiveness (good-looking).

In a series of words correlated with the above synonyms by analogy, units of two types are distinguished: 1) splendid, resplendent, glorious, sublime, superb; 2) exquisite, elegant, choice. The words of the first group are of a general evaluative nature and, in our opinion, can be supplemented by an extensive list of similar words. Noteworthy are the words of the second group:

- elegant - 1) graceful in appearance or manner; 2) tasteful, refined; 3) (of a mode of life etc.) of refined luxury; 4) ingeniously simple and pleasing; 5) 5 US excellent (COD);
- exquisite - 1) extremely beautiful or delicate; 2) acute, keenly felt (exquisite pleasure); 3) keen; highly sensitive or discriminating (exquisite taste) (COD).

In the synonymous dictionaries of the Russian language, we see words denoting the concept of "beauty": 1) beauty, prettiness, beauty; 2) red-gray-haired, beautiful, beautiful, good, handsome b) pretty, cute, cute, pretty, cute (SsinRYa), red, lovely (KrSsinRYa). In a number of nouns, differentiation takes place on the basis of "external - internal" and "poetic - commonly used".

According to the Merriam Webster dictionary the concept "beauty" defines the qualities in a person or thing that as a whole give pleasure to the senses. Besides, the dictionary identifies several synonyms of the concept beauty as following:

➤ *Aesthetics, attractiveness, beauteousness, beautifulness, comeliness, cuteness, fairness, gorgeousness, handsomeness, looks, loveliness, prettiness, sightliness, allure, appeal, attraction, fascination, glamour, charm, delightfulness, elegance, exquisiteness, gloriousness, radiance, radiancy, resplendence, splendidness, sublimeness, desirability, foxiness, lusciousness, nubility, pulchritude, seductiveness, shapeliness, flawlessness, perfection, daintiness, delicacy, flamboyance, flashiness, glossiness, showiness, slickness, splashiness.*

In a number of adjectives, the signs "intensity", "charm", "style characteristics - folk poetic, bookish, colloquial", "clarification of the object of assessment - a child, a young woman, a girl", "a dismissive assessment" are distinguished. As associative words with the concept of "beauty" there are units charming, charming, charming, bewitching, charming, captivating (CsinPЯ). In the interpretation of these words, the signs "conquering power", "appearance, behavior, actions of a person", "intensity", "witchcraft, supernatural power" are actualized.

Comparing the relevant features of synonyms that clarify the concept of "beauty" in English, we can draw the following conclusions:

Coinciding characteristics include the following: a) compliance with the ideal; b) intensity; c) an ironic assessment of a beautiful appearance. The distinguishing features are as follows: 1) the opposition of direct and mentally mediated contemplation (in English); 2) opposition of rational and emotional satisfaction from the contemplation of beauty (in English); 3) accentuated valuation of choice as a basis for aesthetic evaluation (in English); 4) specification of the value of the object of aesthetic evaluation (small size, fragility, delicacy) (in English); 5) specifying the integrity of the object of aesthetic evaluation (purity, freshness, impeccability) (in English).

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